

How to submit your abstract to the IV SymTermes

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Abstract

Here, the Organizing Committee of the IV SymTermes, presents instructions on (i) how to prepare the text of your abstract to the event and (ii) how to upload it to Zenodo repository.

1 Introduction

We proudly announce that all abstracts to be presented at the IV Symposium of Termitology will be deposited at Zenodo¹, the research data repository maintained by CERN (the European Organization for Nuclear Research). All submitted contributions will automatically get a **DOI** identification number (<https://www.doi.org/>). Your abstract will then be fully citable!

Submitted abstracts will be evaluated by the Committee which will decide upon its acceptance straightaway or after some corrections. Full papers will be given a slot of 30 min to be presented orally. Single abstracts (not associated to a full paper may be given a slot of 15 min to be presented orally, if space is available. This process of acceptance of a contribution is described in more detail at Fig. 1.

Once accepted, the abstract will take part of the IV SymTermes Community in Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=symtermes>

Once submitted, a contribution can not be withdrawn from Zenodo, but you can make as many corrections as needed at any times, even after the symposium. Your abstract will be available online, forever, for anyone who wants to discuss it or suggest corrections to it. Each time you make a correction, the previous copy is saved, so that you and anyone else can see all previous versions. See more details in

<http://blog.zenodo.org/2017/05/30/doi-versioning-launched/>

¹Zenodo (<http://zenodo.org>) is part of OpenAire, a network of Open Access repositories, archives and journals supporting Open Access policies

Figure 1: How the Organizing Committee will process the contributions to the IV SymTermes.

2 What kind of contribution should I submit?

Zenodo accepts virtually all types of electronic material, therefore, along with your Abstract you can submit several other related electronic files such as more detailed lecture notes and handouts, figures or even your whole Poster or the slides you plan to use in an Oral Presentation. **Your authorship is guaranteed and preserved by the DOI number.** The Committee will evaluate only the Abstract.

- If you will orally present a **full paper** which is appearing in Sociobiology's 2017 Special Issue on Termites, you can choose to submit any of the following:
 - the paper's abstract. This item is obligatory; the others below are optional.
 - the first draft and posterior versions of the paper (to be treated here as a *Preprint*)
 - the full PDF for the paper in its final version as appearing in the journals
 - the dataset and/or supplementary data used in the paper
 - the lecture notes for your Oral Presentation
 - the slides of your Oral Presentation
 - any other related file
- If you intend to present a **oral presentation**
 - the presentation's abstract. This item is obligatory; the others below are optional.
 - the dataset and/or supplementary data used in the paper
 - the lecture notes for your Oral Presentation
 - the slides of your Oral Presentation
 - any other related file
- If you will present a **poster**
 - the poster's abstract. This item is obligatory; the others below are optional.
 - the electronic PDF version of the poster itself
 - the dataset and/or supplementary data used in the poster
 - any article related to the poster, if allowed by its respective license
 - any other related file

3 How to prepare the text of your abstract

Simply write your abstract in a text editor and save it as `.txt` format, observing the rules and advice provided in the *Abstract Example* below. Please note that the title goes in the first line and the authors and affiliations right after, one author per line.

Abstract example

How to submit a contribution to the IV SymTermes
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SymTermes accepts full papers or single abstracts. Upon acceptance, both contributions will receive a DOI number and become part of the SymTermes Community at Zenodo.org. Accepted full papers will appear in Sociobiology's Special Issue on termites. When writing your abstract, pay attention to the abstract content, not to its aesthetics. For italics, use LaTeX standards: `\textit{Cornitermes cumulans}`. Studies can focus on any aspect of Termitology. Studies using termites as model-organisms on areas other than Termitology can also be accepted, at the discretion of the Committee. Abstracts must include original results from scientific research. We will not accept research proposals, records of species in new localities, or non-scientific and speculative studies. Nomenclatural acts can only be accepted in full papers, at Sociobiology's discretion. Abstracts must be informative, not suggestive: a clear hypothesis or straightforward aim must be declared. We suggest to experimental studies: 2-3 lines for introduction, 2-3 lines for methods and the other lines to write results, discussion and conclusions. The above structure can change, however, it is strongly recommended to clearly present the results in addition to a conclusion indicating how would such results change current knowledge. Abstracts must not exceed 250 words. Acknowledge funding in the last line of the abstract. Funding: CRBio, Vale, Fapemig.

4 How to submit your abstract

Full instructions on how to submit your contribution are given in a video which accompanies this text and is deposited at the SymTermes Community in Zenodo. This video can be found also at YouTube:

<https://youtu.be/eKYjHFk1-Cw> (Portuguese version)

1. Access Zenodo directly through the URL <http://zenodo.org>
2. If it is your first time in the Zenodo website click on **Sign up** and create your account. If you already have an account click on **Log in**. Alternatively, use your ORCID id, if you have one.
3. Click on “Communities” to access SymTermes Community.
4. Search for IV Symtermes community entering the word “symtermes” in the search box shown at the top of the page.

5. Click on "View" displayed in the "IV Symposium of Termitology" box.
6. Click on "Upload" displayed at the bottom of the website.
7. Choose your file clicking on "Choose files" and then open it or directly drag it on the "Files" window. Here you should upload at least your abstract in format `.txt`.
8. Upload your file clicking on "Start upload". If all is ok "Saved successfully" will be displayed.
9. Choose either "Poster" or "Presentation" as it applies to your case.
10. Fill in the blank boxes. In the box "Description", copy and paste the text of your abstract as it is presented in the file you have uploaded above. Please make sure to upload **ONLY** the text, that is, to not copy and paste the title and the author names, as these are already declared in the blank boxes.
11. Finally click on "Publish" (5).
12. If the submission is ok the DOI number will be displayed. That number identifies your abstract in both the IV Symtermes and future citations.